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Constitution of association panel of tropical field corn (Zeamays L) for kernel and cob-related traits --Manuscript Draft--

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Author Comments:	Development of association panel of tropical field corn (Zea mays L) for kernel and

cob-related traits comprising Indian based maize germplasm is first of its kind. The information generated may be utilized for decision making in maize improvement

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Constitution of association panel of tropical field corn (*Zea mays* L) for kernel and cob-related traits

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Abstract

Maize is one of the model crops for genetic study and has wider variability for yield component traits. Capturing the available variability and utilizing it in the breeding program is the prerequisite for the maize improvement program. On the other hand, the energy and resources required to characterize the germplasm are huge and maintenance of the trait becomes challenging when the population size of the germplasm is large. However, based on the concept of a mini-core collection, the breeder can capture maximum variability by sampling the entire germplasm available and utilizing them in an active crop improvement program. Similarly, the present panel of inbred lines, 'Field Corn Panel of IARI', was constituted to use them in trait mapping followed by active utilization in the field corn breeding program of IARI. This panel may serve as the base study material for GWAS analysis, genomic prediction, and identification of tolerant inbred lines for biotic and abiotic stresses and yield component traits, etc. In the present study, a detailed discussion has been made on the construction of a subset of maize germplasm from the available whole set of field corn germplasm of IARI by capturing the maximum variability present.

Keywords: Germplasm, core-hunter, field corn, panel, molecular diversity, PCA

Introduction

Maize has wider genetic variability and phenotypic diversity that can be effectively exploited in maize improvement programs to improve productivity (Flint-Garcia et al., 2005). Identification of novel genetic variations and mapping of the genomic regions governing the variability is of utmost importance to utilize them in such breeding programs. There are different strategies for capturing these variations in cross-pollinated species like maize. As an outbred species, maize encompasses a high level of phenotypic and molecular diversity. When considering nucleotide diversity, any two random maize lines differ from one another in 1.4% of total DNA, similar to

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4 the divergence observed between humans and chimpanzees (Buckler and Stevens 2005). This
5 kind of variation can be mapped by using different approaches *viz.*, linkage or QTL mapping,
6 and association or linkage disequilibrium (LD) mapping (Xu et al., 2018) to dissect the trait *vis-*
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8 *à-vis* breeding perspectives. Maize by its enormous genetic variability (Cooper et al., 2019),
9 availability of SNP information, and rapid LD decay (Mazaheri et al., 2019), make this an ideal
10 crop for GWAS (Xiao et al., 2017). The requirement of a genetically variable population
11 becomes a prerequisite for the mapping of traits underlying natural variations.
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17 An ideal population should harbor as much genetic diversity as possible, which is often used to
18 resolve complex trait variation to a single gene or nucleotide. Screening of available germplasm
19 to make a workable collection followed by their utilization in trait mapping may help in
20 fastening the process of trait discovery through association mapping approaches. However,
21 careful selection of germplasm to include existing variation is a challenge since breeder cannot
22 use existing wide variability in the given crop for their improvement followed by their
23 maintenance. Udupdhyia and Ortiz (2001) suggested the concept of deriving a mini-core
24 collection or subset population by capturing the maximum variability available in the core
25 population and their ease of handling in subsequent genetic analysis followed by usage of the
26 same in the breeding program.
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32 In India, there is limited information available about the formulation of the subset of germplasm
33 harboring extensive variability present in the tropically adapted germplasm (Udupdhyia et al.,
34 2012). In this direction, an effort has been made to construct a subset or panel of tropical maize
35 germplasm available in the Indian maize breeding program.
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38 **Material and method**

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42 A germplasm collection consisting of 514 distinct genotypes derived from different source
43 populations was used as a base material for this study. These genotypes were evaluated using
44 augmented design during the *Kharif-2020* at ICAR-IARI, PUSA, New Delhi. Data on yield and
45 related traits such as Cob Length (CL) (cm), Cob Diameter (CD) (cm), Kernel Row Number
46 (KRN) (No.s), Kernels per Row (KPR) (No.s), Shelling Percentage (SH%), and Grain yield
47 (kg/ha) were recorded and subjected to statistical tools (R package) to calculate descriptive
48 statistics, principal component analysis (PCA), correlation and phenotypic diversity analysis.
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50 Further, the population was also subjected to Core Hunter 3.0 (<http://www.corehunter.org/r.html>)
51 to narrow down the number of genotypes by keeping its diversity intact. Subsequently, the
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4 generated subset of 200 genotypes from the main population and six elite breeding lines were
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6 combinedly (206 genotypes) evaluated under augmented design during *khariif* 2021 at the ICAR-
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8 IARI, PUSA campus, New Delhi. Five randomly selected plants were used to record the data on
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10 CL, CD, KRN, and KPR and grain yield.

11 Descriptive statistics and a two-sample Welch's *t*-test (Welch 1947), were used to compare the
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13 unequal sample size, original (514), and derived (206) populations, assuming unequal variance.
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15 The formula followed for Welch's *t*-test was as follows.

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

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23 Where \bar{x}_1 and \bar{x}_2 are the sample means, s_1^2 and s_2^2 are the sample variances, and n_1 and n_2 are
24
25 the sample sizes.

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27 In addition, a total of 24 SSR markers linked to yield components and heterosis were used to
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29 profile these 206 genotypes. DNA was extracted from fresh young leaves of genotypes by the
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31 CTAB (Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide) method (Saghai-Marooif et al. 1984). The PCR was
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33 performed with 1 unit of Taq DNA polymerase, 10× reaction buffer supplied by the
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35 manufacturer, 0.1 mM dNTPs, 10 pmol/μl each primer and 50 ng DNA template in a total
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37 reaction volume of 25 μl. The PCR amplification conditions were, initial denaturation at 94°C for
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39 5 min followed by 35 cycles consisting of denaturation at 94°C for 30 s, annealing at 55°C for 30
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41 s, extension at 72°C for 60 s and a final extension of 7 min. at 72°C. The PCR-amplified
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43 fragments were resolved on 2.5% agarose gel (HiMedia) and gel pictures were archived in a gel
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45 documentation framework.

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47 The detection of alleles and determination of their sizes were accomplished through an image
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49 processor (UNITEC Cambridge). The scoring of the number of peaks and profiles per marker
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51 was done by checking the amplification in different accessions. A data matrix involving 62
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53 accessions was then generated, with entries indicating the presence (1) or absence (0) of the
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55 amplified SSR fragments. The polymorphic information content (PIC) for each SSR locus was
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57 computed using the formula mentioned below.

$$PIC = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i^2 - \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n 2p_i p_j$$

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4 where: n – number of alleles; p_i – frequency of the i^{th} allele; p_j – frequency of the j^{th} allele
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6 (Botstein et al. 1980). The molecular diversity was assessed using Darwin Software
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8 (<https://Darwin.cirad.fr>).
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10 **Results and Discussion**

11 The descriptive statistics of 514 genotypes indicated that a wide range of variability exists for
12 each trait. Cob length ranged from 5.5 to 21.45 cm with a mean value of 13.52 cm. Cob diameter
13 recorded a mean of 3.295 cm and it ranged from 1.43 cm to 4.56 cm. The mean values for Kernel
14 Row Number (KRN) and Kernels per Row (KPR) were found to be 14 and 27.55, respectively.
15 The KPR was found to have a range of 11.4 to 48.45, while for KRN it was 10 to 22. Similarly,
16 the mean Shelling percentage recorded was 70.91%, with a range of 62.24 to
17 89.10%. The grain yield ranged from 480 kg/ha to 5810 kg/ha with a mean of 2090 kg/ha (Table
18 1). The existing variability in the core population itself can directly be utilized in the maize
19 improvement program (Antony et al., 2024). However, due to the problem in handling such
20 variability, one should classify the total variability into its components followed by the grouping
21 of genotypes based on the major components (Upadhyaya et al., 2012; Syafii et al., 2015). In the
22 present study, the PCA analysis (Fig.1) subdivided total variability into six different components,
23 which can also be utilized for prioritizing the traits for selection (Bradu and Gabriel, 1978). The
24 highest eigenvalue was recorded by cob diameter (2.83) followed by cob length (1.05). On the
25 other hand, the lowest eigenvalue was recorded grain yield (0.16) followed by shelling
26 percentage (0.32). Kernel-related traits *viz.*, KRN and KPR exhibited eigenvalues, 1.01 and 0.63
27 respectively (Table 2). Cob diameter contributes through PC1(0.49) and PC2 (0.14) and cob
28 length contributes majorly through PC6 (0.67) and PC1 (0.49). The KPR contributes mainly
29 through PC1 (0.53) and PC5 (0.29) and KRN was through PC2 (0.54) and PC5 (0.46) Similarly,
30 PC1(0.4) and PC3 (0.23) were coordinated by Shelling percentage, whereas grain yield was
31 contributed by PC2 (0.72) and PC3 (0.63) (Table 2). This information can be further utilized for
32 selecting the genotypes for trait-based crop improvement (Daudo and Olakojo, 2007).
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34 Further phenotypic data on CL, CD, KRN, KPR, SH%, and grain yield were subjected to the
35 correlation of traits among the diverse germplasm comprising 514 genotypes as per the method
36 given by Pearson (Pearson, 1901) to understand the relative association of traits among each
37 other (Mukri et al., 2021). Notably, KPR exhibited a significantly positive correlation with CL
38 (0.72) and yield (0.48). Cob diameter showed a positive and significant association with KRN
39 (0.72) and yield (0.48). Cob diameter showed a positive and significant association with KRN
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4 (0.49) and yield (0.43). Shelling Percentage indicated a significant positive correlation with grain
5 yield (0.53). In addition, intercorrelation among these four traits showed that they also have a
6 significant association with each other (Fig. 2) and also influence the expression of grain yield
7 positively (Kumar et. al., 2017, Nagarajan and Nalla thambi, 2017; Yi Q et. al., 2019).
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11 Having known variability and association between traits, the genotypes were subjected to
12 diversity analysis. The hierarchical cluster method indicated that the genotypes under study were
13 equally distributed to all coordinates and spread across ten groups (Mukri et al., 2018) suggesting
14 high phenotypic diversity among them (Fig. 3). Further, this set of 514 genotypes was subjected
15 to Core-hunter 3.0 with 38% selection intensity (Thachuk et al., 2008). Using both the
16 information together, a subset of 200 genotypes was then carefully selected from the original
17 pool of 514 inbred lines which is a representative subset of the maize germplasm
18 maintained at IARI, New Delhi. Six breeding lines that are already in use at the IARI maize
19 breeding program were added to the 200 selected genotypes that combinedly constitute the
20 “Field Corn Panel of IARI”. Subsequently, this entire set of 206 inbred lines was evaluated over
21 the next growing season to revalidate (Upadhyaya et al., 2003) and ascertain the extent of
22 variability.
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25 For the 206 genotypes comprising the ‘Field Corn Panel of IARI’, the mean values for CL, CD,
26 KRN, KPR, and grain yield were calculated to be 11.96 cm, 3.28 cm, 13.12, 19.47, and 2355
27 kg/ha respectively. Similarly, the median recorded for the traits viz., CL, CD, KRN, KPR, and
28 grain yield were 11.50cm,3.26cm,13.00,19.33, and 2.26 (t/ha) respectively. The corresponding
29 ranges for CL, CD, KRN, KPR and grain yield were found to be 7.17 cm to 20.4cm, 1.88-4.85
30 cm, 8 to 24, 9.33 to 36.33 and 649-5469 kg/ha, respectively (Fig. 4). Considering the deviation
31 between the means and median of the population (514) and the selected Field Corn Panel of
32 IARI (206), it was understood that variation present in the population (514) is available in the
33 panel derived from the same too (Upadhyaya and Ortiz., 2001). However, according to Welch's t-
34 test, due to the unequal variance, CL, KRN, KPR, and grain yield showed significant differences
35 among the original population and panel, but CD recorded non-significant differences (Table 3).
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37 On the other hand, there is no significant deviation among the range of each trait available in
38 both the original population and panel (Hu et al., 2000, Kim et al., 2007). Hence, it is an
39 opportunity for breeders to capture and exploit the total variability that existed in the original
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4 population (514) by executing the selection strategy in the newly constituted panel (Upadhyaya
5 et al. 2006).

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8 To understand the molecular diversity available in the panel, the 206 genotypes were subjected to
9 molecular characterization with 24 SSR (Simple Sequence Repeat) markers spanning 10
11 chromosomes (Kumar et al., 2021, Patil et al., 2023). The molecular diversity analysis indicated
12 that the extracted subset (panel) harbors diverse inbred lines. The 206 inbred lines are further
13 divided into ten clusters containing 5 to 42 inbred lines (Fig. 5). This distribution supports a high
14 level of molecular diversity existed among the genotypes (Samiha et al., 2024), suggesting
15 substantial genetic variability within the studied 'Field Corn Panel of IARI' (Zhang et al., 2012).
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20 21 **Conclusion**

22 The constitution of the panel of maize is a prerequisite for the genetic analysis targeting trait
23 dissection and mapping. Considering the amount of energy required for maintaining the
24 germplasm *vis-a-vis* capturing the maximum variability for the crop improvement program. The
25 Constitution of a panel comprising the breeding material available in the IARI maize breeding
26 program was undertaken. The newly constituted "Field Corn Panel of IARI" harbors available
27 variability present in the whole germplasm of the field corn breeding program of IARI. Further,
28 the breeder can select, and utilize the promising lines for the maize improvement program along
29 with the trait dissection.
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37 **Authors contribution**

38 GM, Conceptualized, designed, and planned the experiment. GM, NCG, and Dhandapani
39 performed the statistical analysis and GM, RNG, and Shilpa prepared the manuscript. DP, CS,
40 and JSB facilitated the conduct of experiments and data collection. All authors have read, edited,
41 and approved the final draft of the manuscript.
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48 the ICAR-BMGF project for financial support.
49
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51 **Declaration of competing interest**

52 All the authors have no conflict of interest to declare.
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55 **Data availability**

56 Data will be available on request.
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59 **Informed consent**

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4 Informed consent was acquired from all independent participants involved in the current
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6 study.

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Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Yield Component Traits among 514 genotypes

Particulars	Cob Length(cm)	Cob Diameter(cm)	Kernel Row Number (No.s)	Kernels per Row (No.s)	Shelling%	Grain Yield(t/ha)
Observations	514	514	514	514	514	514
Mean	13.52	3.295	14	27.55	70.91	2.09
Std.Deviation	2.922	0.6055	2.38	7.128	10.45	1.066
Minimum	5.5	1.43	10	11.4	62.24	0.48
Maximum	21.45	4.56	22	48.45	89.1	5.81

Table 2: Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors of the correlation matrix for yield component traits

S.No.	Traits	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6
1	Cob Diameter	2.83	1.78	0.47	0.47	0.49	0.14	-0.25	0.08	-0.81	-0.05
2	Cob Length	1.05	0.04	0.17	0.65	0.49	-0.31	0.23	0.36	0.17	0.67
3	Kernel per Row	1.01	0.38	0.17	0.81	0.53	-0.21	0.19	0.19	0.29	-0.72
4	Kernel Row Number	0.63	0.31	0.11	0.92	0.27	0.54	-0.63	0.12	0.46	0.09
5	Shelling Percentage	0.32	0.16	0.05	0.97	0.40	0.14	0.23	-0.86	0.10	0.13
6	Grain Yield	0.16	-	0.03	1.00	-0.02	0.72	0.63	0.27	-0.05	-0.01

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Table 3: Welch's unequal variances *t*-test for testing the trait means among germplasm and Field Corn Panel of IARI

No. of Genotypes		Cob Length (cm)	Cob Diameter (cm)	Kernel Row Number (No.s)	Kernels per Row (No.s)	Grain Yield (t/ha)
Mean	514 (Germplasm)	13.52	3.29	14.00	27.55	2.09
	206 (Field Corn Panel of IARI)	11.96	3.28	13.12	19.47	2.35
Median	514 (Germplasm)	13.52	3.29	14.00	27.55	2.09
	206 (Field Corn Panel of IARI)	11.50	3.26	13.00	19.33	2.25
Welch <i>t</i> -test		7.39	1.59	5.70	20.11	2.26

Figure 1: Principle Component Analysis of major yield component traits of 514 genotypes

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Figure 2: Correlation between yield and yield component traits

Figure 3: Formation of groups based on Hierarchical cluster analysis comprising 514 genotypes

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Figure 4: Variability for cob and kernel traits among 206 genotypes

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Figure 5: Depiction of Diversity among the Field Corn Panel of IARI by SSR markers